

Practice Abstract no. 41

Accelerating research and innovation in data-driven food solutions

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

Building on the findings of the workshop and breakout room sessions, the following recommendation and driving actions was proposed:

Recommendation: Accelerate research and innovation in data-driven food solutions.

Proposed Actions:

- 1. Fund cross-disciplinary research:** Funding programmes and calls for proposals should be designed to allocate resources to projects that bridge disciplines. Specifically, funds should support interdisciplinary collaborations that integrate data science, AI, food science, environmental science, and social sciences (including active citizen engagement) to tackle complex challenges within the food system.
- 2. Encourage data-driven product development:** Making data more widely available, transparently and responsibly, is expected to benefit companies and other food system actors. This will facilitate the development of healthier and more sustainable products that align with data-based consumer demands and contribute to the EU's environmental objectives.
- 3. Support "regulatory sandboxes" for AI experimentation:** AI has integrated most people's daily lives, and therefore, it is crucial to maximize the opportunities it offers while remaining cautious. A key focus should be on accelerating the adoption and development of AI in food systems, potentially through the creation of "regulatory sandboxes." These sandboxes would serve as controlled environments for companies, research organizations, and other stakeholders to develop and test innovative AI applications. This approach could foster collaborative learning among various actors, including legislators and regulators, to pinpoint opportunities, potential risks, and unintended consequences. This collaborative process is essential for ensuring the safe and ethical deployment of AI technologies.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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